

This is the tile year space twin paradox, which is made of the following components: The terrain clock paired with the land clock, the extra of the sea clock, and the outcome of the air clock, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired terrain clock with the land clock, then sea clock, however, if sea clock, then air clock, however, if air clock, then paired terrain clock with the land clock. This twin paradox explained and shown before is, once again, name the tile year space twin paradox.

This set is timed as 1:01, and is dated as the 10th day of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.